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Annelids as models of germ cell and gonad regeneration

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28 **ABSTRACT**

29 Germ cells (reproductive cells) give rise to the next generation in sexually reproducing
30 organisms. The loss or removal of germ cells lead to sterility in established research organisms
31 such as the fruit fly, nematodes, frog, and mouse. The failure to regenerate germ cells in these
32 organisms reinforced the dogma of germline-soma barrier in which germ cells are set-aside
33 during embryogenesis and cannot be replaced by somatic cells. However, in stark contrast,
34 many animals including segmented worms (annelids), hydrozoans, planaria, sea stars, sea
35 urchins, and tunicates can regenerate germ cells. Here I review germ cell and gonad
36 regeneration in annelids, a rich history of research that dates back to the early 20th century in
37 this highly regenerative group. Examples include annelids from across the annelid phylogeny,
38 across developmental stages and reproductive strategies. Annelids can recover germ cells after
39 ablation of germ cell progenitors in the embryos; and adult annelids regenerate germ cells as a
40 part of regeneration, grafting, and asexual reproduction. I present a framework to investigate
41 cellular sources of germ cell regeneration in annelids, and discuss the literature that support
42 different possibilities within this framework, where germ-soma separation may or may not be
43 preserved. With contemporary genetic-lineage tracing and bioinformatics tools, and several
44 genetically-enabled annelid models, we are at the brink of answering the big questions that
45 puzzled many for over more than a century.

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60 **1. Introduction**

61 Animals establish a set of cells, the germline, that pass on their genetic material from one
62 generation to the next. Germline is typically viewed as strictly separate from the rest of the
63 cells that make up the organism's body, collectively called soma (Nussbaum, 1880; Weismann,
64 1893; Klein, 1917). This germline-soma separation has been argued as necessary for several
65 reasons including for maintaining genome integrity in the germ cell lineage, for epigenetic
66 reprogramming, and for maintaining telomere length so that organisms do not age with each
67 successive generation (Wright et al., 1996; Castañeda et al., 2011; Hajkova, 2011; Ozturk, 2015;
68 Eguizabal et al., 2016; Labbé et al., 2017; Fernández and González-Vasconcellos, 2018; Gleason
69 et al., 2018; Bloom et al., 2019; Gruhn et al., 2023). In contrast, somatic cells are viewed as an
70 aging cell population and once the germline is segregated from soma during embryogenesis,
71 somatic cells do not contribute to the reproductive cell pool (Weismann, 1893; Buss, 1983;
72 Johnson et al., 2011; Monaghan and Metcalfe, 2019). While this dichotomous view of germline
73 and soma holds true for many extensively studied model organisms (e.g. *Drosophila*,
74 *Caenorhabditis elegans*, mouse), many organisms do not fit into this strict mold (Stephenson,
75 1930; Heys, 1931; Bounoure, 1940; Stéphan-Dubois, 1964; Buss, 1988; Weisblat, 2006; Özpolat
76 et al., 2016; Tadokoro, 2018; Wessel et al., 2020). In some organisms the germline can be
77 recovered upon loss of reproductive organs or ablation of the primordial germ cells. In some of
78 these cases, the source cells that replace the lost germline are of somatic origin (Kawamura et
79 al., 2011; Yajima and Wessel, 2011; Wessel et al., 2014a; Yoshida et al., 2017). In other
80 organisms, germline can be re-established after many cycles of asexual, agametic reproduction
81 (Ghiselin, 1987; Brusca and Brusca, 2003; Sunanaga et al., 2006; Sköld et al., 2009). Different
82 groups of animals have evolved a range of strategies for this plasticity. Sponges, *Hydra*, and
83 planarian flatworms have pluripotent stem cell populations in the adults that continuously
84 produce and regenerate germ cells (Wang et al., 2007; Isaeva, 2011; Issigonis and Newmark,
85 2019; Holstein, 2023). Sea star larvae recover lost germ cells after larval bisection, and as adults
86 they regenerate gonads during whole-body regeneration (Inoue et al., 1992; Wessel et al.,
87 2014b). Tunicate larvae also recover lost germline upon tail amputation and become fertile as
88 adults (Kawamura et al., 2011; Yoshida et al., 2017). Zebrafish and salamanders can regenerate
89 gonads if a part of the gonad containing the germline stem cells remains after surgery (White et
90 al., 2011; Erler et al., 2017). Finally, plants repeatedly make their germline from somatic cells, as
91 they do not have germline segregation (Schmidt et al., 2015; Walbot and Egger, 2016).
92 Altogether, these organisms defy many of the assumptions about the germline that originate
93 from the studies on established model organisms, mainly that germline is a set-aside lineage
94 that needs to be segregated and protected, and if lost, it cannot be replaced. However, while
95 we know many organisms can regenerate their germ cells, in many of these examples, we still
96 do not know how germ cell regeneration is accomplished, and whether the source cells are of
97 somatic origin.

98 The focus of this review is a group of highly regenerative organisms, annelids (or segmented
99 worms), which regenerate their germ cells and gonads, and go through asexual-sexual cycles

100 where the germline appears discontinuous. Therefore, annelids show high plasticity around
101 making and re-making their germline in different contexts and at different developmental
102 stages. Annelid germ cell and gonad regeneration has been reviewed previously focusing on a
103 limited number of annelids (Weisblat, 2006; Özpolat and Bely, 2016; Özpolat et al., 2016;
104 Tadokoro, 2018; Wessel et al., 2020). In this review, I cover extensive literature going back to
105 the late 1800s and published in many languages. To my knowledge, there is no other animal
106 group this topic has been studied in such breadth. Annelids are diverse and highly regenerative,
107 many are easy to access and rear for the full life cycle and easy to observe under a microscope.
108 Therefore, this rich history of studies reflect the feasibility of annelids as models of germ cell
109 and gonad regeneration. With the contemporary tools and technologies available to
110 developmental biologists, we can now add more depth to these studies. Here, I present a
111 framework to investigate the possible cellular sources of the regenerated germline in the
112 context of whether germline continuity across generations (i.e. germ-soma separation) is
113 preserved or not. This approach will allow identifying cellular sources, and eventually the
114 molecular underpinnings of germ cell and gonad regeneration.

115 **2. General anatomy and diversity of reproductive systems in annelids**

116 Annelids are a large group and over 21,000 species have been described (Rouse et al., 2022).
117 Most annelids have vermiform body morphology, with repeating organs and tissues in each
118 segment. Segments are capped with asegmental tissues on either anterior or posterior ends
119 (Fig. 1A). In some annelids, segments are physically separated from each other via a membrane
120 called septum, while some annelids do not have this structure, therefore have a continuous
121 coelomic (fluid-filled) cavity. Recent molecular phylogenetic analyses group annelids into two
122 major clades, Sedentaria and Errantia, while several annelid lineages branch basally (Struck et
123 al., 2011; Weigert and Bleidorn, 2016). Clitellata (“oligochaetes” and leeches) is nested within
124 Sedentaria, which also includes sedentary “polychaetes”, while Errantia is composed mainly of
125 “polychaetes” (Fig. 1B). Within and across these clades, annelids show a large diversity of
126 reproductive anatomies and strategies (Giese and Pearse, 1975; Schroeder and Hermans, 1975;
127 Dorresteijn and Westheide, 1999), making them a rich group to investigate germline plasticity
128 and regeneration in different contexts and across different life stages.

129 Clitellates are exclusively hermaphroditic, have localized gonads which typically appear in the
130 same segments in a species-specific manner (Brinkhurst and Jamieson, 1971; Lasserre, 1975;
131 Loden, 1981; Christensen, 1994) (Fig. 1B’). For example, in the hermaphrodite earthworm
132 *Eisenia*, two pairs of testes are found in segments 10 and 11, and a pair of ovaries are found in
133 segment 13 (Gates, 1949). Therefore, it is possible to amputate worms into small fragments
134 that are (in theory) completely somatic except for these specific gonad-bearing segments, and
135 ask if somatic fragments can regenerate into sexually-mature adults. Errant and Sedentary
136 “polychaetes”, on the other hand, are generally gonochoric (either male or female) but
137 hermaphroditism is also observed (Schroeder and Hermans, 1975) (Fig. 1B). Polychaetes
138 typically have germ cells and gonads present more widely across the body (Fig. 1B’). Some

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140 **Figure 1 - Phylogeny of annelid species and distribution of processes**

141 **A)** Annelid body plan shows generalized regions: Segments are capped by two asegmental regions called
 142 prostomium (pro.) and pygidium (pyg.). Anterior to the pygidium resides the posterior growth zone
 143 (PGZ) where new cells and segments are generated by two concentric rings of stem cells called
 144 teloblasts. Some annelids have physical separation of segments via membranes called septae. Segment
 145 numbering shown for a few anterior segments.

146 **B)** Phylogenetic relationship of species and processes covered in this review (Struck et al., 2011; Weigert
 147 et al., 2014)

148 **B')** Examples of gonad/germ cell distribution and general features are depicted for specific groups
 149 (indicated by the black bars). Cartoons are simplified annelids illustrating the general distribution of
 150 gonads (not the exact segment location in the species). MPC: Multipotent Progenitor Cells; AC: anterior
 151 cluster

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155 polychaetes have segment specific location of gonads similar to clitellates, while some do not
156 have localized gonads and instead use the entire body (the coelomic cavity) as a gamete
157 incubator. Meanwhile, others such as Syllids undergo schizogamy (Franke, 1999), where they
158 produce sexual clones (stolons) that bud off (Ponz-Segrelles et al., 2018).

159 Annelids have stereotypical embryonic development, similar to *C. elegans* and *Ciona*
160 development, where cells in the embryo undergo precise cleavages and give rise to cell lineages
161 with predetermined fates (Wilson, 1892; Conklin, 1897; Sulston et al., 1983; Nishida and Satoh,
162 1985). As a part of this embryonic program, primordial germ cells (PGCs) are thought to arise
163 via maternally-inherited factors and from the 4d cell lineage (Stéphan-Dubois, 1964; Kang et al.,
164 2002; Oyama and Shimizu, 2007; Rebscher et al., 2012; Fischer and Arendt, 2013; Rebscher,
165 2014; Özpolat et al., 2017). This appears to be the case in all annelids studied to date (Rebscher,
166 2014). The PGCs arise within the gonadal segments in clitellates. In errant and sedentary
167 polychaetes, PGCs form and then migrate to their final location. It is currently not known
168 whether PGCs form both somatic and germ components of the gonads, or whether the somatic
169 contribution is made via other tissues. In the species that form gonads, these organs may be
170 formed on the septae or the coelomic epithelium as pear-shaped structures, and gradually
171 develop into fully mature sexual organs. Secondary sexual characteristics such as seminal
172 vesicles, ovisacs, ducts, clitellum etc... may not appear until full sexual maturation (Brinkhurst
173 and Jamieson, 1971; Brusca and Brusca, 2003).

174 **3. Germline regeneration in the context of embryonic regulation**

175 To test if embryos can recover from and grow into fertile adults after the ablation of the germ
176 lineage during early embryogenesis, the embryonic cell that gives to PGCs was ablated (either
177 4d or 3D) in *Capitella* (Amiel et al., 2013; Dannenberg and Seaver, 2018) (Fig. 2E). In this
178 sedentary polychaete, 4d gives rise to the PGCs and the anus only, however this cell is very
179 small and hard to ablate. Therefore, the majority of manipulations were carried out on its
180 precursor (3D), which gives rise to part of the endoderm, in addition to PGCs and the anus.
181 Germline-ablated (3D-deleted) samples were first raised to stage 7 larvae (about 7 days post
182 fertilization) and these larvae overall had similar morphology to controls. When 3D-deleted
183 larvae were analyzed further for *piwi1* expression, there was an overall expansion of *piwi1*
184 expression but with loss of the characteristic PGC signal (Amiel et al., 2013). In the controls,
185 *piwi1* is expressed in the PGCs and the posterior growth zone only. When these experiments
186 were repeated in a later study, authors found that in stage 9 larvae, about 87% of the larvae
187 lacked the PGCs, but 13% regenerated them even though the blastomere that normally
188 produces them was ablated (Dannenberg and Seaver, 2018). Interestingly, the rate of
189 individuals with regenerated germline significantly increased in juvenile stages (nearly 100%).
190 Authors suggest there are 2 phases of germline regeneration: one during embryonic/larval
191 stages with limited success, and another phase post-metamorphosis with higher success. When
192 raised to adulthood, the 3D-deleted individuals are fully fertile with all parts of the reproductive
193 system present, and can mate to produce viable progeny. To get more insight into which

194 lineage may be contributing to the regenerated germline, authors hypothesized that the source
 195 would be of mesodermal origin, and tested this hypothesis by deleting the 2D blastomere. This
 196 experiment effectively ablates the left mesoderm and the germline (the right mesoderm
 197 originates from another blastomere, and therefore is still present). When raised to adulthood,
 198 while the survival was lower (only 6%), both males and females were fertile and able to mate.
 199 Therefore, authors conclude that 2D (precursor of left mesoderm) is not the source of the
 200 regenerated germline, and the precursor of the right mesoderm (3c) remains to be tested as
 201 the potential source. *Capitella* has genetic tools established, and therefore in future
 202 experiments it is feasible to combine long-term lineage tracing and blastomere ablation
 203 experiments, dissecting the origins of the regenerated germline in this embryonic germline
 204 ablation model.

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207 **Figure 2 - Examples of gonad and germ cell regeneration in annelids**

208 **A)** Gonads regenerate via epimorphosis as a part of body axis regeneration, in this example during
 209 anterior regeneration. **B)** Gonads regenerate via morphallaxis (tissue reorganization) in original but
 210 previously non-gonadal segments. **C)** Germ cells regenerate via epimorphosis. **D)** Gonads regenerate in
 211 transplanted segments. **E)** The germline regenerates after the ablation of the germline precursor in the
 212 embryo. Blue color denotes gonadal tissues or germ cells. Gray color denotes newly-regenerated
 213 segments. Anterior to the left, dorsal up.

214 **4. Germ cell and gonad regeneration as a part of whole-body axis regeneration**

215 Most annelids regenerate at least posteriorly after bisection, many annelids regenerate both
216 anteriorly and posteriorly from small body fragments (Figs. 1B, 2) (Bely, 2006; Bely et al., 2014;
217 Kostyuchenko and Kozin, 2021). During regeneration, annelids may employ blastema-based
218 regeneration (epimorphosis) and tissue remodeling (morphallaxis) (Özpolat and Bely, 2016).
219 Epimorphic regeneration is a process that results in the creation of new tissues through cell
220 proliferation. These cells form a regeneration blastema and eventually differentiate into new
221 tissues. This type of regeneration involves a series of stages, including wound healing, blastema
222 formation, blastema patterning, differentiation, and growth. Morphallactic regeneration
223 restores missing structures by remodeling existing tissues, without blastema formation (Özpolat
224 and Bely, 2016). In the context of germ cell and gonad regeneration, epimorphic regeneration
225 would involve regenerating the germ cells and gonads in the newly regenerated segments (Fig.
226 2A, 2C), while morphallaxis would be reorganizing previously non-gonadal segments into
227 gonadal segments (Fig. 2B).

228 It is important to note that, even if gonadal structures regenerate, this may not be sufficient
229 proof for germ cell regeneration (e.g. perhaps only somatic components of gonads regenerate
230 without any germ cells). Ideally, gametes would be observed in regenerated gonads and the
231 ultimate test would be whether the regenerated individuals can sexually reproduce and give
232 rise to fertile progeny. Some studies reviewed below have been able to show fertility after
233 regeneration, while others could not (but always for technical reasons such as worms only
234 asexually reproduce in laboratory conditions) (Fig. 1B).

235 **4a. Germ cell and gonad regeneration during epimorphic regeneration**

236 It has been possible to test whether worms have the capacity to regenerate sexual organs from
237 parts of the body that normally do not have the gonads in clitellates, because this group
238 generally displays restricted localization of gonads to specific segments. There are multiple
239 examples of clitellates regenerating germ cells and gonads in previously non-gonadal segments,
240 even though studies vary in their approach. Experiments in *Criodrilus*, *Enchytraeus*,
241 *Lumbriculus*, *Perionyx*, *Rhynchelmis* all show that gonads regenerate, while in some of these
242 species, the position, number, or the sex of regenerated gonads may vary from the control
243 worms that were not amputated.

244 Victor Janda extensively studied germ cell and gonad regeneration in *Criodrilus lacuum* and
245 *Rhynchelmis limosella* (Janda, 1912a; b, 1924, 1926), and these appear to be the first extensive
246 works on the subject. Janda removed gonad-bearing segments from *Criodrilus*, and observed
247 successful germ cell and gonad regeneration eventually with female or male gametes forming.
248 In his initial studies (Janda, 1912a; b), Janda used hundreds of mostly-medium sized worms,
249 some showing clear external characteristics of sexual maturation. He amputated 17-30 anterior
250 segments which included the entire sexual region (Fig. 3C-D). The anterior pieces were fixed,
251 and posterior pieces were let regenerate. Some of these regenerating samples were fixed after

252

253 **Figure 3 - Examples of reproductive anatomies in different annelids**

254 **A)** *Pristina leidy* (a clitellate naidid), is hermaphroditic, and gonads always appear in segments 6 and 7.
 255 Gonads, fission zones, and the posterior growth zone all express germline/multipotency markers.
 256 arrowheads indicate some of the *piwi+* cells on the ventral nerve cord. Inset (**A'**) shows the *piwi+* cells
 257 from the ventral view (adapted from (Özpolat and Bely, 2015))

258 **B)** *Platynereis dumerilii* (an errant polychaete) is gonochoric, and does not have localized gonads.
 259 Instead gonial clusters are distributed along the body (shown by *vasa* expression). Adapted from (Kuehn
 260 et al., 2021)

261 **C)** Cartoon of a frontal section of *Criodrilus*. Ovaries (yellow) and testes (blue) as well as secondary
 262 sexual structures such as seminal vesicles and ducts are shown (Janda, 1912a). This species has septae in
 263 between segments.

264 **D)** Schematics showing the normal distribution of gonads (bottom) and the supernumerary gonads that
 265 extend beyond gonadal segments in *Criodrilus* (top) (Janda, 1912a).

266

267 5 months, others were raised further. Janda observed that germ cells and gonads always
 268 regenerated, he never found worms that failed to regenerate germ cells and gonads (Fig. 1B).
 269 Just as during development, the pear-shaped gonads appeared first, and the secondary sexual
 270 characteristics formed later. Some regenerated ovaries were significantly larger than normal
 271 ovaries. Interestingly, supernumerary ovaries and testes in the regenerated worms appeared at
 272 a high frequency; ovaries were always more numerous than testes, some regenerated worms

273 had only ovaries but never all testes (Fig. 3D). In unamputated worms, ovaries are found only in
274 segment 13 as a single pair, and there are only 2 pairs of testes in segments 10 and 11. In
275 regenerated worms there were pairs of ovaries and testes found in many other segments, for
276 example ovaries were observed in multiple consecutive segments (e.g. segments 8-13, or
277 segments 4-18). Also, supernumerary regenerated gonads appeared in segments they normally
278 do not occupy in normal worms. These tended to be shifted anteriorly, sometimes ovaries
279 replacing testes, which were shifted to further anterior segments. Janda's *Rhynchelmis*
280 *limosella* findings were similar to *Criodrilus*: worms could always regenerate germ cells and
281 gonads during anterior regeneration, usually with a positional shift and supernumerary, but not
282 as extensive as in *Criodrilus* (Janda, 1924). Positional shift or supernumerary gonads after
283 regeneration have also been observed in several other clitellates. In *Lumbriculus* gonad number
284 and positional variability are observed in regenerated worms (Mrázek, 1906). In *Enchytraeus*
285 regenerated gonads along with germ cells are always observed in the 7th and 8th segments
286 (Myohara et al., 1999; Tadokoro et al., 2006), even though gonads develop normally in 10th and
287 11th segments (Christensen, 1994; Sugio et al., 2008). In *Perionyx excavatus* during anterior
288 regeneration, gonads and sex apparatus regenerate, but are found at variable locations
289 compared to controls (Gates, 1927).

290 Only a handful of studies show successful sexual maturation after regeneration in clitellates. In
291 *Criodrilus*, Janda reared the regenerated worms for 2-4 years and observed that supernumerary
292 gonads persisted long after amputation (Janda, 1912a). These worms sometimes had
293 abnormalities in the morphology or placement of their sexual apparatus, but they were
294 nevertheless fertile and gave rise to viable progeny even 3 years after the operation. He then
295 carried out extended analyses in a later study where he tested the effect of different conditions
296 on gonad regeneration in *Criodrilus*, including repeated amputation-regeneration cycles (Janda,
297 1926). In the repeated amputation-regeneration experiment, 15-17 anterior segments were
298 removed at first (samples used were either adults or very young worms). Gonads were re-
299 formed as many times as the operation was carried out (up to 7 times of amputations) in both
300 age groups. Even when regeneration was abnormal, these animals still mated and produced
301 viable progeny. This work in *Criodrilus* and Janda's other works in *Rhynchelmis* are the first
302 examples in annelids where regenerated germ cells and gonads are shown to give rise to viable
303 progeny. Similarly, more recent studies in *Enchytraeus* showed that this clitellate can also
304 regenerate germ cells and gonads and become sexually mature from fragments that do not
305 contain previously gonadal segments (Myohara et al., 1999; Tadokoro et al., 2006). When
306 worms were cut into 3 fragments (only the anterior piece containing the gonadal segments),
307 the majority of the middle and posterior pieces and all the anterior pieces regenerated and
308 became sexually mature (Tadokoro et al., 2006).

309 In "polychaetes", studies that obtain small non-gonadal fragments and grow into full worms do
310 not exist. This is in part due to the anatomical differences between polychaetes and clitellates:
311 polychaetes typically have gonads or germ cells spread more widely across the body (e.g. more
312 pairs of gonads in numerous segments, or coelomic gonial clusters which are not confined to

313 gonadal structures but instead are freely floating across the body) (Fig. 1B'). Another reason is
314 the scarcity of polychaete regeneration laboratory models which can regenerate both anteriorly
315 and posteriorly, thereby eliminating the possibility to obtain a small worm fragment which can
316 regenerate into a complete worm (Fig. 1B). Nevertheless, experiments in *Capitella*, *Nephtys*,
317 *Platynereis*, and *Spirorbis* show extensive removal followed by successful regeneration of germ
318 cells and gonads.

319 *Capitella* and *Platynereis* juvenile worms can only regenerate posteriorly. In both groups, there
320 is a cluster of cells anteriorly located and expressing germline multipotency markers (Fig. 1B',
321 3B). Posterior regeneration only takes place if amputation is carried out posterior to this
322 "anterior cluster". Nevertheless, this amputation removes the majority of germ cells and
323 gonads both in *Capitella* and *Platynereis*, and worms regenerate the entire body axis, including
324 the male and female gonads (in *Capitella*) or male or female gonial clusters (in *Platynereis*)
325 (Metzger et al.; Hofmann, 1966; Hauenschild and Fischer, 1969; Giani et al., 2011; Rebscher,
326 2014). Therefore, in either case, while complete removal of the germ cells is not possible with
327 simple bisections, the majority of germ cell and gonadal tissues can be removed and will
328 regenerate during body axis regeneration. Future studies that employ genetic ablation of germ
329 cells will be able to test whether these species still regenerate germ cells without the anterior
330 cell clusters that express germline markers.

331 The timeline of gonad and germ cell regeneration appears to be uncoupled from body axis
332 regeneration in many polychaetes. In *Platynereis*, posterior regeneration is completed in about
333 5-7 days (Planques et al., 2018), however, regeneration of gonial clusters takes a lot longer,
334 often several weeks (Metzger et al.). Similar observations were made in *Nephtys*, where after 3
335 weeks of regeneration, Clark observed rudiments of nephridia and a complex of gonadal blood
336 vessels appear but no gonads and no signs of gametogenesis until later (Clark, 1968).
337 Contradicting with these observations, Stagni reported oocytes regenerated only a few days
338 into anterior body axis regeneration in the sedentary polychaete *Spirorbis* (Stagni, 1959).
339 However, it is unclear if these worms had some remaining germ cells in the stump that went
340 under an accelerated maturation. Successful sexual maturation and fertility after germ cell
341 regeneration has not been tested in these studies except for *Platynereis* (Fig. 1B). *Platynereis*
342 reaches sexual maturation after regeneration, there is no significant change in oocyte number
343 in females, success of fertilization both in males and females, and F1 progeny of the
344 regenerated males and females are also fertile (Metzger et al.).

345 4b. Germ cell and gonad regeneration as a part of morphallaxis and dynamic tissue 346 maintenance

347 Annelids dynamically maintain body proportions as they grow posteriorly and when they
348 regenerate. In the context of germ cell and gonad regeneration, the dynamic maintenance
349 could mean making new gonads in previously non-gonadal segments, or regressing and
350 regrowing gonads based on nutrient availability (Figs 2B, 4C). A striking example of this is
351 morphallaxis. Morphallaxis is a regenerative process where pre-existing tissues and organs are

352 reorganized following injury or damage to form new structures. Unlike epimorphosis, which
353 generates new tissues mainly via cell proliferation and formation of a blastema, morphallaxis is
354 thought to involve existing cells, tissues, and organs without blastema formation (Özpolat and
355 Bely, 2016). For example, in *Pristina*, worms only regenerate 4 segments via epimorphosis
356 during anterior regeneration, even when more than 4 anterior segments are removed. This
357 results in a worm that has abnormal body proportions: depending on where the amputation is
358 made, the worm may have posterior segments starting immediately after the head segments,
359 while missing the mid-body segments along with the gonads (Fig. 2B). The correct body
360 organization and proportions are re-established via morphallaxis following epimorphic
361 regeneration (Özpolat and Bely, 2016; Özpolat et al., 2016). This has also been shown in
362 *Enchytraeus* using regional gut markers (Myohara et al., 1999; Takeo et al., 2008) and in *Eisenia*
363 which only regenerates 5-6 anterior segments irrespective of the number of anterior segments
364 removed (Gates, 1949). Therefore, in the “oligochaetes” *Enchytraeus*, *Pristina*, and *Eisenia*, if
365 anterior amputation removes a large enough region that includes the gonadal segments, the
366 number of segments regenerated anteriorly will not include the gonadal segments during the
367 epimorphic phase. Instead, the worms will reorganize the more posterior and previously non-
368 gonadal segments into gonadal segments via morphallaxis (Fig. 2B).

369 Similar plasticity and dynamic maintenance of gonads is also observed in experiments where
370 nutrient availability was altered (Fig. 4C). In *Eisenia*, starving and re-feeding the worms induces
371 supernumerary gonads in previously non-gonadal segments, sometimes along with sex
372 inversion where testes turned into ootestes (Herlant-Meewis, 1962; Relexans, 1970). In
373 *Enchytraeus* and *Pristina* gonads regress upon starvation and reform upon refeeding in lab
374 conditions (Myohara et al., 1999; Özpolat and Bely, 2015). While these are not experiments
375 involving injury and regeneration, they demonstrate dynamic maintenance and ability to grow
376 gonads that are naturally occurring in annelids.

377 **5. Germ cell and gonad regeneration upon surgical removal and transplantation**

378 Another way to approach gonad and germ cell regeneration is to surgically remove these
379 organs and cells and test whether the operated worms regenerate them. However, in practice
380 these are difficult experiments in many annelid models due to small organismal size, or
381 presence of numerous pairs of gonads or germ cells across the body that would have to be
382 removed as is the case in many polychaetes. Therefore, experiments involving surgical removal
383 or transplantation have been carried out mainly in the earthworm *Eisenia*, because this species
384 is large and easy to surgically manipulate (Avel, 1929; André and Davant, 1977).

385 A neat set of grafting experiments in *Eisenia* tested whether gonads would regenerate along
386 with the germ cells after surgical removal (André and Davant, 1977) (Fig. 2D). A several-
387 segments-long piece containing the gonads was obtained. This piece was then flipped inside
388 out (like a sock), and all organs including gonads were removed. Then the piece was reversed
389 back and grafted onto a control worm (Fig. 2D). These grafts were able to regenerate gonads, in
390 some cases the regenerated gonads in the grafts reached full sexual maturity and formed

391 mature gametes. In other cases, different stages of oogenesis and spermatogenesis were
392 observed, or there were small buds of gonads that failed to fully differentiate where it was not
393 possible to determine the sex. Regeneration of sexual organs was always partial, and different
394 parts of the reproductive system (including the secondary sexual characteristics, such as
395 seminal vesicles) regenerated independently of each other. In rare cases, all the sexual organs
396 and apparatus were present at the same time, but in reduced numbers. For example, there was
397 one testis instead of four. Interestingly, the digestive tract never regenerated, and the nervous
398 system only regenerated in some grafts. However, the absence of these tissues did not affect
399 gonad regeneration. Nephridia usually regenerated along with the gonads. But when nephridia
400 did not regenerate, gonads nevertheless regenerated and, in some cases, reached full sexual
401 maturity including gametes. Authors also tested different grafting locations (gonadal region vs
402 non-gonadal) in the host, which did not influence the success of gonad regeneration. Overall,
403 gonads and germ cells could robustly regenerate in these experiments, especially compared to
404 all the other organs and tissues.

405 **6. Germ cell and gonad re-establishment without embryogenesis**

406 An organism may undergo various morphological, physiological, and behavioral changes that
407 are essential for its growth, survival, and reproduction as a part of post-embryonic
408 development. Examples include metamorphosis in insects, growth and differentiation of organs
409 and tissues in animals, and asexual reproductive processes such as fission and budding in many
410 organisms. I will primarily focus on asexual reproduction (paratomic and architomic fission),
411 stolonization, and posterior growth in this section (Fig. 4A, 4B). These are processes during
412 which new germ cells and gonads are produced post-embryonically.

413 **6a. Paratomic and architomic fission**

414 Fission is an asexual reproduction mode where an individual divides into two or more new
415 individuals, and this type of reproduction is observed across annelid taxa. In paratomic fission,
416 worms first start developing new tail and new head portions, and then split into two complete
417 individuals, or sometimes form chains of clonal worms that eventually separate. In architomic
418 fission, worms fragment themselves into small pieces (sometimes as small as a single segment)
419 via constriction of circular muscles, then each of these pieces develop (“regenerate”) into new
420 individuals. There are many fissioning species in clitellates (Harper, 1904; Mrázek, 1906;
421 Dehorne, 1915, 1916; Stephenson, 1930; Berrill, 1952; Lasserre, 1975; Schroeder and Hermans,
422 1975; Loden, 1981; Christensen, 1994; Myohara et al., 1999; Zattara and Bely, 2011, 2016;
423 Özpolat and Bely, 2015), but the ability is not restricted to clitellates and examples in
424 polychaetes are also found (Malaquin, 1905, 1925; Faulkner, 1930; Gibson and Harvey, 2000;
425 Marescalchi et al., 2019).

426 In natural and lab populations of several clitellate species such as *Enchytraeus*, *Lumbriculus*,
427 *Pristina*, and *Stylaria* (Harper, 1904; Mrázek, 1906; Dehorne, 1916; Christensen, 1973, 1994)
428 and in some polychaetes such as *Pygospio* (Gibson and Harvey, 2000) asexual and sexual

429 reproduction alternate (Fig. 4A). In some species, population density (or culture density in the
430 lab) can trigger the shift: in low density conditions (a few worms) worms may sexually mature,
431 while in high density they will primarily asexually reproduce (Christensen, 1973). Sometimes
432 there may be many generations of asexual reproduction before some worms in a population
433 become sexual again. In *Pristina* lab cultures, it was estimated that even after thousands of
434 asexual generations, worms still make gonads during each asexual reproduction cycle. Sexual
435 individuals are observed although very rare (Özpolat and Bely, 2015). In many Naididae,
436 including *Pristina*, gonads are made on the septae of newly-produced segments during
437 paratomic fission (Christensen, 1973; Özpolat and Bely, 2015). How gonads and the germ cells
438 are maintained and/or re-established through numerous asexual cycles is unknown.

439 In *Enchytraeus*, sexually mature worms undergo architomic fission (fragmentation into small
440 pieces), and then the fragments that develop into whole worms can eventually become sexually
441 mature (Myohara et al., 1999). In species that fission via paratomy, new gonads are gradually
442 produced as new head segments develop, and in some of these species, cells that express
443 germline markers are observed to migrate towards segments where new gonads are made
444 (Özpolat and Bely, 2015). It is unclear if architomic species “expect” an upcoming fission event,
445 and distribute germline progenitors across all segments, so that fission results in pieces that can
446 re-establish gonads. Alternatively, worms can re-make gonads from cells present in the
447 segments, without relying on the germline specifically. (See below for more discussion on
448 source cells.)

449 Genital segments are rebuilt after autotomy as a part of the natural life cycle in the errant
450 polychaete *Eunice* (Hofmann 1972, 1974). In this species, there are about 70 to 150 genital
451 segments containing gonads and gametes. These genital segments are located posteriorly and
452 they separate from the rest of the body via autotomy, leaving worms with only non-gonadal
453 segments. Upon “regeneration” of missing segments, gonads are re-established along with
454 gametes, and worms can reproduce again (Hofmann 1972, 1974).

455 6b. Stolonization

456 A fascinating group of errant polychaetes called Syllids make clones (stolons), sometimes
457 forming chains of clones, in a process called stolonization (Franke, 1999) (Fig. 4B). Some Syllids
458 also alternate between asexual fragmentation and sexual stolonization (Okada, 1929; Berrill,
459 1952; Ribeiro et al., 2020). While superficially stolonization appears similar to what happens in
460 asexual fission, there is a key twist: unlike asexual fission, the clones in stolonization are
461 produced with the sole purpose of *sexual* reproduction in Syllids (Malaquin, 1893; Berrill, 1952;
462 Schroeder and Hermans, 1975; Franke, 1999). In some Syllids, it has been suggested that
463 oocytes or sperm are produced by and passed to the stolons from the gonads of the anterior
464 “stock” worm (Gidholm, 1963; Wissocq, 1966; Franke, 1999). In some of these older studies,
465 histological analyses show that ovaries are present only in the stock worm and not the stolons,
466 and that gametes from the stock are transferred to the stolons via a special canal (Gidholm,
467 1963). Therefore, there is strong histological evidence of gamete transfer into stolons in Syllids.

468 However, there is a more recent study using molecular markers that suggest *de novo* formation
 469 of gametes and gonads in the stolons simultaneously with the stock worm (Ponz-Segrelles et
 470 al., 2018). Further studies are needed to show the exact origins of gametes in the stolons, and
 471 investigate whether some germ cells are established *de novo* in the stolons via cell lineage
 472 analyses.

473

474

475 **Figure 4 - Examples of germ cell plasticity and formation without embryogenesis in annelids**

476 **A)** Asexual-sexual cycles, and formation of new gonads without embryogenesis shown for paratomic
 477 fission. In some species, the asexual cycles and new gonad formation during asexual reproduction may
 478 happen for 100s of cycles before the organism undergoes sexual reproduction.

479 **B)** Stolonization in Syllids depicted. The stock worm (most anteriorly located) has gonads, the clones
 480 (called stolons) forming at the tail end contain mature gametes. These stolons detach from the stock,
 481 reproduce sexually, and die.

482 **C)** Dynamic regression and reformation of gonads during starvation-refeeding cycles. In many annelids,
 483 gonads regress upon starvation, and reform once nutrients are available again.

484 Blue color denotes gonadal tissues or germ cells.

485

486 **6c. Posterior growth**

487 One of the annelid hallmarks is posterior growth from a localized ring of cells at the tail end
 488 (segment addition zone) (Balavoine, 2014). Most annelids retain their growth zone throughout
 489 their life and continuously add new segments. Cells in the growth zone express
 490 germline/multipotency markers (Gazave et al., 2013; Özpolat and Bely, 2016). Because of
 491 molecular signature similarity of the growth zone to germ cells, and the pluripotent nature of
 492 these stem cells as a population (Álvarez-Campos et al., 2023a), they cannot be ruled out as a

493 potential secondary source of germ cells in addition to the primordial germ cells established
494 during embryogenesis (Rebscher et al., 2012; Rebscher, 2014; Özpolat et al., 2017). As the new
495 segments are being established, new gonads or germ cells could be made as a part of the
496 posterior growth process. While there is no direct evidence supporting this possibility yet, it has
497 been suggested in the polychaete *Perinereis* (Maceren-Pates et al., 2015). Overall, annelids can
498 continuously produce germ cells and gonads via asexual fission, stolonization, and posterior
499 growth. Several examples presented here highlight that the clones and segments produced this
500 way contain germ cells, but it is still unclear whether the germline is transferred to the clones
501 and new segments, or whether they are made *de novo*.

502

503 **7. Cellular mechanisms of regenerating the germ cells**

504 Cells that participate in regeneration have been of great interest in this field of research
505 because determining the source cells (e.g. whether regeneration involves pluripotent stem cells
506 such as neoblasts or cell de-differentiation and/or transdifferentiation) is critical for
507 understanding the mechanisms of regeneration (Poss, 2010; Vierbuchen et al., 2010; Jopling et
508 al., 2011; Tanaka and Reddien, 2011; Vogt, 2012; Ereskovsky et al., 2019; Pesaresi et al., 2019).
509 Source cells can tell us how cells respond to injury and are reprogrammed, or how organisms
510 fail or succeed in regenerating based on the availability of cell types and their potencies. While
511 the source cell question is one of many approaches to the mechanistic understanding of
512 regeneration in general, I argue that it becomes a central question for germ cell regeneration:
513 because the germline has been viewed as a set-aside and continuous cell lineage in metazoans,
514 depending on the cell type(s) that replace the germ cells during regeneration, continuity of this
515 lineage may be preserved or broken (MacCord and Ozpolat, 2019) (Fig. 5). It is important to
516 know whether this is the case, because, if somatic cells are the source cells (i.e. discontinuity in
517 germ lineage), mutations they carry may be passed on to the regenerated germ cells, and
518 consequently they may have poor genome integrity. On the other hand, organisms that
519 regenerate their germ cells primarily from somatic tissues may have evolved mechanisms to
520 retain genomic integrity, and understanding how they manage high levels of genome integrity
521 in their somatic cells will be greatly informative. Finally, if organisms evolved ways to keep the
522 germline intact and continuous across injury-regeneration cycles, or asexual-sexual cycles, how
523 they achieve maintaining a dormant germline across the body through these cycles will also be
524 greatly informative.

525 In this section, I aim to first establish my definitions for possible cell sources in germ cell
526 regeneration, and then discuss the annelid literature in this context. Overall, my definitions are
527 strictly based on historical definitions of germ and soma as cell lineages established during
528 embryogenesis. I regard germline as a cell lineage that gets segregated during embryonic
529 development with the sole purpose of eventually giving rise to the gametes in the adults. Any
530 cell type that comes from this initial set of cells and will give rise to gametes is considered the
531 germline or germ cells (e.g. primordial germ cells, germline stem cells, mature gametes...).

532 Soma is any other cell type in the body such as muscle, neurons, gut etc, that do not contribute
 533 to the germline under normal circumstances (i.e. normal growth and maturation) once the
 534 germline is established (the Weismann barrier) (Weismann, 1893; Nieuwkoop and Sutasurya,
 535 1979, 1981; Extavour and Akam, 2003).

536 What complicates this dichotomy is animals that have adult pluripotent stem cell types (such as
 537 i-cells in hydrozoans, or neoblasts in planarians and acoels) (see Solana 2013 for an extensive
 538 discussion on this topic (Solana, 2013)). Data are scarce on the exact embryonic origins of these
 539 pluripotent cells, and therefore it is hard to categorize them as germline or soma in the
 540 traditional sense (Davies et al., 2017; Kimura et al., 2022; Varley et al., 2023). However, they
 541 can give rise to both soma and germ cells throughout life in these organisms (Heys, 1931;
 542 Bounoure, 1940; Buss, 1988; Newmark et al., 2008; Gold and Jacobs, 2013; Solana, 2013).
 543 Therefore, I consider these as a third cell type (pluripotent) which cannot be categorized as
 544 soma or germline until we have more information about their embryonic origins and their post-
 545 embryonic potential (i.e. whether they have subpopulations that are strictly dedicated to giving
 546 rise to the germline) (Fig. 5A vs 5B).

547

548 **Figure 5 - Framework for investigating cellular sources of germ cell regeneration**

549 **A-C)** Models of cellular sources in germ cell regeneration. Some organisms may have adult pluripotent
 550 cells that can regenerate both somatic and germ cells (A). In others, there may be lineage-restricted cell
 551 populations that can only regenerate somatic or germ cells (B). Finally, some organisms may be able to
 552 regenerate germ cells using their somatic cells via dedifferentiation or transdifferentiation. Blue: germline;
 553 Yellow: soma; Gray: pluri/multipotent cell.

554 **D)** Continuity of germline, and break in the continuity, if soma is the source of regeneration. (Adapted
 555 from (MacCord and Ozpolat, 2019))

556 **7a. Models for Cellular Sources of Germline Regeneration**

557 The cellular basis of new tissues generated in annelids during regeneration, posterior growth,
558 and asexual reproduction is still an open question and an active area of investigation. While the
559 exact source cells and their potencies are not entirely known, there are several lines of
560 evidence that suggest that annelids do not have adult pluripotent stem cells such as planarian
561 neoblasts. In regeneration, most new cells and tissues are thought to arise from cells nearby
562 the wound site (Boilly, 1967, 1969; Bely, 2014; Bely et al., 2014; Planques et al., 2018; Ribeiro et
563 al., 2018, 2021; Bideau et al., 2021, 2023; Kostyuchenko and Kozin, 2021). New cells in the
564 zones of growth (especially posterior growth) are thought to arise from a population of cells
565 that altogether have pluripotency but sub populations have more limited potencies, and the
566 individual potencies of these cells are yet to be determined (Gazave et al., 2013; Balavoine,
567 2014; Álvarez-Campos et al., 2023a).

568 The term “neoblast” was originally coined in annelids upon observations of cells that appeared
569 to have migratory characteristic and a large nucleus to cytoplasmic ratio, accumulating around
570 the wound site during regeneration (Randolph, 1891, 1892). However, these cells are only
571 found in clitellates, and generally not found in sedentary or errant polychaetes (Boilly, 1969;
572 Potswald, 1969; Bely, 2014). Even in clitellates, the nature of neoblasts and whether they are
573 pluripotent or restricted in their potential, and whether they are even required for
574 regeneration is still debated. Indeed, several lines of evidence suggest that annelid neoblasts
575 are not necessary for regeneration. For example, in the clitellate *Enchytraeus*, two sister species
576 were compared, one with neoblasts and another without (Myohara, 2012), but both species are
577 able to regenerate and therefore neoblasts do not appear necessary for regeneration in this
578 genus (in contrast to planarian neoblasts, which are necessary for regeneration). In another
579 study, cells that fit the historical description of annelid neoblasts (i.e. cells with large
580 nucleus/cytoplasm ratio and migratory) were found to be strongly related to fission and
581 formation of new gonads during fission but not anterior or posterior regeneration in *Pristina*
582 (Özpolat and Bely, 2015). Overall, while neoblasts have been widely studied in annelids for over
583 a century, so far there is no strong evidence for individual pluripotent neoblasts that can give
584 rise to all tissue types and germ layers including the germ cells in annelids. Therefore, all three
585 models (Fig. 5) still need to be tested via contemporary methods such as genetic lineage tracing
586 or single cell sequencing across the regeneration, asexual reproduction via fission, or posterior
587 growth timelines. Below, I will review the existing literature and list evidence supporting each
588 mechanism.

589 **7a1. Mechanism 1: Pluripotent lineages (e.g. neoblasts) (Fig. 5A)**

590 Clitellate neoblasts are described as cells that reside on septae (the membrane that separates
591 segments from each other), seen across many segments, and become migratory when there is
592 an injury (Randolph, 1891, 1892; Hill, 1970; Bely, 2014). In their migratory form (sometimes
593 referred to as “wandering cells”) they are typically found ventrally, especially on the ventral
594 nerve cord. However, these cells are not universal in annelids, and even within the same

595 species they may be observed migrating towards the posterior wound but not the anterior
596 wound, though both axes can regenerate (Herlant-Meewis, 1946; Berrill, 1952; Zattara et al.,
597 2016). In *Enchytraeus*, neoblasts have been studied extensively, and while there is evidence for
598 these cells to migrate to the wound site and participate in blastema formation, these studies
599 did not include lineage tracing that could resolve whether *Enchytraeus* neoblasts are
600 pluripotent or not (Tadokoro et al., 2006). As mentioned above, some *Enchytraeus* species do
601 not have neoblasts, but can regenerate nevertheless (Myohara, 2012).

602 In “polychaetes” fewer studies from the molecular era investigated neoblasts and their role in
603 regeneration. Generally, works that studied regeneration from a neoblast perspective are
604 relatively older, and had the limitations of using static images of histological preps or not having
605 access to molecular tools for labeling. One recent study in *Capitella* suggests cell migration to
606 the blastema, but acknowledges that these may be lineage-restricted stem cells instead of
607 neoblasts (de Jong and Seaver, 2017). While there were several older works claiming the
608 existence of neoblasts in polychaetes, many also disagreed (Boilly, 1969; Potswald, 1969).
609 Specifically, several works focusing on germ cell regeneration suggested that germ cells
610 regenerated from neoblasts (Malaquin, 1925; Faulkner, 1930; Jyssum, 1957; Stagni, 1959;
611 Vannini, 1965). In *Spirorbis*, oocytes were suggested to regenerate in a matter of days from a
612 conspicuous reserve of neoblasts, distributed along animal’s body, but were particularly evident
613 at the achaetic region (a few specific segments without chaetae in *Spirorbis*) (Stagni, 1959).
614 However, later studies disagreed with the neoblast-driven germ cell regeneration observations,
615 arguing that these studies confuse blood vessel structural cells with neoblasts (Potswald, 1969,
616 1972). It is evident in Potswald’s language in his titles (e.g. “so-called neoblasts”) that he was
617 strongly against the presence of neoblasts as source cells in regeneration. He quotes Hill (Hill,
618 1970): “Perhaps it is time to stop evoking ‘reserve’ cells to explain all of the mysteries of
619 regeneration.”

620 Interestingly there is one publication which argued that germ cells give rise to all tissue types in
621 *Filograna* and *Salmacina*, claiming they act like neoblasts (Malaquin, 1905). According to
622 Malaquin, germ cells multiply via mitosis inside each segment, then these cells infiltrate the
623 septae or between the epidermis and muscle, and later participate in forming the fission zone.
624 He likens this to germline cancers, where germ cells can give rise to other types of tissues. This
625 is the only work that I have encountered in annelids where germ cells are claimed to give rise to
626 somatic cells during regeneration. But Faulkner disagrees with Malaquin and says that these are
627 not gonocytes, but instead they are neoblasts that are functionally identical with germ cells and
628 are the only cells that retain the potential to proliferate to make new tissues (Faulkner, 1930).
629 Similarly in another study in *Filograna*, Faulkner suggested that the production of the fission
630 zone entails tissue disintegration, followed by new tissue formation (all 3 germ layers) via
631 neoblasts located in the ventral body wall. Overall, there is no strong and direct evidence for
632 pluripotent neoblasts that migrate across several segments to participate in regeneration in
633 annelids where they can give rise to both somatic and germ cells. It is more likely that migratory
634 cells sometimes mistakenly are referred to as “neoblasts”, and these cells may be associated
635 with building new tissues including gonads during asexual reproduction than regeneration
636 (discussed in the next section), and therefore represent a lineage-restricted cell type.

637 **7a2. Mechanism 2: Lineage restriction (Fig. 5B)**

638 Lineage restriction as a mechanism of regeneration has been suggested in organisms such as
639 axolotl, zebrafish, and mouse (Kragl et al., 2009; Jopling et al., 2010; Kikuchi et al., 2010;
640 Lehoczky et al., 2011; Flowers et al., 2017; Cao et al., 2019, 2021; Johnson et al., 2020; Sanor et
641 al., 2020). Two levels of lineage restriction can be considered: 1) restriction at the embryonic
642 germ layer or 2) restriction at the cell type level. If cells that originated from one germ layer
643 give rise to cell types of only their original germ layer (e.g. mesoderm derivatives regenerate
644 mesoderm cell types only) they can be considered lineage restricted at the germ layer level. If
645 cells can give rise to cell types outside of their original germ layer, then they are likely to be
646 considered pluripotent. A stricter approach to lineage restriction would focus on the individual
647 cell types, and whether a cell type can regenerate only the same differentiated cell type (e.g.
648 muscle cells regenerate new muscle). In the germ cell regeneration context, considering the
649 cell-level lineage restriction is more relevant, because we are concerned with germline-soma
650 separation, and whether the germline continuity is preserved or not. The embryonic germ
651 layers are too broad and therefore not helpful, because germ cells in annelids have
652 mesodermal origin during development, where they share embryonic lineage with other cell
653 types such as muscle and connective tissues (Wilson, 1892; Pilon and Weisblat, 1997; Rebscher,
654 2014; Özpolat et al., 2017). This makes it still possible to have a somatic to germ
655 transdifferentiation even if there is germ layer level lineage restriction during regeneration,
656 which has been suggested in annelids (Cornec et al., 1987; Bely, 2014).

657 Lineage restriction in terms of germ and soma is established early in the annelid life cycle,
658 where the germline is established and set aside early during embryogenesis (Rebscher, 2014).
659 The mechanism of germline specification is thought to be via maternal determinants, and once
660 the germ cells are set aside, somatic cells are believed not to contribute to this lineage
661 anymore. It is then possible that annelids may have a dedicated germ cell lineage which
662 specifically participates in regenerating the germ cells or re-establishing them during asexual
663 reproduction, therefore keeping the lineage continuous. In this section, I will review examples
664 that support this scenario.

665 In *Enchytraeus*, *piwi+* cells were suggested to migrate into regeneration blastema and possibly
666 take part in regenerating the gonads specifically (Tadokoro et al., 2006). These *piwi+* cells are
667 thought to be different from the cells described as neoblasts in *Enchytraeus*, both in terms of
668 location and behavior during regeneration (Tadokoro et al., 2006; Sugio et al., 2008, 2012;
669 Yoshida-Noro and Tochinai, 2010). *piwi+* cells proliferate in original segments after amputation,
670 and then are thought to migrate to regenerate gonads. This migration occurs at a later stage
671 than neoblast migration to blastema. Neoblasts participate in the formation of blastema first,
672 while *piwi+* cells arrive after the blastema has been formed, therefore authors of the work
673 interpret this as these two cell populations having distinct roles in regenerating separate tissues
674 and organs, which would support the lineage restriction scenario. However, the authors also
675 discuss, it is still possible for *piwi+* cells to give rise to more than the gonads (therefore they

676 could be multipotent, supporting mechanism 1). It is also possible that the neoblasts that
677 migrate earlier to the blastema eventually also participate in gonad regeneration. Lineage
678 tracing with contemporary techniques is needed to resolve these open questions.

679 In *Criodrilus*, Janda alluded to the presence of “latent sex cells” that help regenerate the
680 gonads. These cells are located on the ventral part of the body, are dormant until needed, and
681 migrate both anteriorly and posteriorly during regeneration (Janda, 1926). He comments on
682 some ongoing experiments to test whether he can exhaust this “stem” population that allows
683 regenerating gonads by repeatedly amputating and obtaining small fragments from regenerates
684 for many (re)generations. However, I was unable to find this publication and it is unclear
685 whether he published his findings from this experiment. He notes that “it remains to be seen
686 whether the latent sex cells result from the mere transformation of originally "somatic" and
687 differentiated cells, or whether they present themselves from the beginning as independent,
688 even if hidden and undifferentiated sex elements, which are only activated under suitable
689 conditions.”

690 In *Capitella*, gonads regenerate during posterior body axis regeneration. Authors suggest
691 anteriorly-located *vasa+* cluster of cells migrate posteriorly to regenerate gonads (de Jong and
692 Seaver, 2017; Seaver and de Jong, 2021), though in an earlier study (Giani et al., 2011) it was
693 suggested there is not any migration from this cell cluster (called multipotent progenitor cells
694 or MPCs). Similarly, in *Platynereis*, if amputation removes all the germline including the cluster
695 of cells always located anteriorly in segments 6-8 (Fig. 3B), worms fail to regenerate the
696 posterior body axis (Hofmann, 1966; Zelada González, 2005; Kuehn et al., 2021; Álvarez-
697 Campos et al., 2023b). If the amputation is carried out leaving the anterior cluster intact, while
698 removing the majority of the germline, worms regenerate the entire body along with the germ
699 cells (Metzger et al.). It is possible at least some of the regenerated germ cells come from the
700 anterior cluster, however, there is currently no direct evidence.

701 During asexual reproduction in clitellates, including in *Criodrilus*, *Enchytraeus*, *Nais*,
702 *Lumbriculus*, *Pristina*, several workers observed “wandering cells” which appeared migratory
703 especially along the ventral nerve cord (Iwanow, 1903; Janda, 1926; Herlant-Meewis, 1946;
704 Berrill, 1952; Lasserre, 1975; Sugio et al., 2008; Yoshida-Noro and Tochinai, 2010; Özpolat and
705 Bely, 2015; Kostyuchenko and Smirnova, 2023). Some of these works suggested these to be
706 neoblasts that would participate in regeneration. I hypothesize that these cells possibly have a
707 separate role, which is to transmit germline across asexual cycles of reproduction. However,
708 most evidence is indirect. In *Nais* these cells are congregated along the nerve cord and
709 accumulate in the segments where the fission zone appears (Herlant-Meewis, 1946). In two
710 *Pristina* species, *piwi+* or *vasa+* cells that fit the histological definitions of previous studies in
711 *Nais* and other Nais are also found on the ventral nerve cord (Özpolat and Bely, 2015;
712 Kostyuchenko and Smirnova, 2023). Some of these *piwi+* cells come into close contact with the
713 gonads, and live-imaging suggests they primarily migrate towards the fission zone where new
714 gonads are being established (Özpolat and Bely, 2015). In the “polychaetes” *Filograna* and

715 *Salmacina*, migratory cells during asexual reproduction have been observed and argued to be
716 germ cells (Malaquin, 1905). It is possible that at least Clitellate annelids have a set-aside cell
717 population that may be primarily involved in actively building new gonads during asexual
718 fission, which is reminiscent of colonial organisms such as tunicates (Rodriguez et al., 2017).

719 Finally, the posterior growth zone has been suggested as a potential post-embryonic source of
720 germ cells in *Perinereis*. A model is proposed where primordial germ cells stay in the posterior
721 growth zone instead of migrating and forming an anterior cluster of germ cells, in contrast to
722 *Platynereis* (Maceren-Pates et al., 2015). In this model, PGCs that remain in the growth zone
723 give rise to the gonial clusters each time a new segment is produced.

724 **7a3. Mechanism 3: Somatic lineages (Fig. 5C)**

725 Several lines of evidence suggest somatic cell dedifferentiation during regeneration and asexual
726 reproduction. In the context of germ cell regeneration, this widespread dedifferentiation
727 becomes a potential source of regenerated germ cells from formerly somatic cells. One work
728 that directly supports soma to germ transition is the embryonic ablations in *Capitella* as
729 discussed above. However, all works carried out in juveniles and adults are indirect lines of
730 evidence.

731 In the clitellate *Eisenia*, transplantation of segments containing only somatic tissues results in
732 gonad regeneration (André and Davant, 1977). Authors suggest non-gonadal mesodermal
733 structures (somatopleure and septae) within the graft as the source of regenerating gonads,
734 and that the host tissues do not contribute to regeneration, therefore germ cells are not
735 migrating from the host into the grafted segments to regenerate gonads. In *Lumbricillus*, there
736 are no reserves of unspecialized cells in the form of neoblasts; however, ordinary mesoderm
737 cells were suggested to regenerate the genital organs (Herlant-Meewis, 1946a). In *Enchytraeus*,
738 Myohara either artificially amputated worms to make small fragments from all along the body,
739 or induced the worms to naturally fragment (Myohara et al., 1999). Depending on which region
740 needed to be regenerated, gonads regenerated either via epimorphosis or morphallaxis. Even
741 though this work only systematically looked at the gut as a read out of normal regeneration,
742 some of the previously non-gonadal small fragments regenerated and became sexually mature.
743 While this can be seen as a line of evidence for soma to germ conversion, it is also possible
744 these worms have a dormant lineage of germ cells dedicated to regenerating/re-establishing
745 the germline (as discussed above) (Yoshida-Noro and Tochinai, 2010). Similarly, in older studies
746 mentioned above, at the histological level Janda and others did not find evidence of gonads or
747 related structures outside of the segments that have been described as gonadal, and concluded
748 that non-gonadal segments can produce gonads from somatic tissues. But these workers did
749 not have access to molecular tools, therefore the possibility of a germ cell reserve across the
750 body cannot be ruled out. In the “polychaete” *Nephtys*, during late stages of regeneration,
751 gonads were observed to regenerate via histological analyses of a series of frontal sections
752 (Clark, 1968). Dividing fibroblasts with epithelial origin are suggested as the source cells for
753 regenerating different tissues, including gonads. Overall, while there is compelling evidence for

754 somatic origin for regenerated germ cells, future studies using genetic lineage tracing are
755 required to show direct lineage relationships of somatic cells with the regenerated germ cells.

756 **8. What lies ahead**

757 Discussions of whether somatic cells contribute to germ cell and gonad regeneration go back to
758 the late 19th century when Weismann's and Nussbaum's theories of germ plasm or germ line
759 continuity were first postulated (Nussbaum, 1880; Weismann, 1893; Stockberger, 1913; Klein,
760 1917). These theories became widely accepted, but there were many researchers who also
761 challenged them (Janda, 1926; Heys, 1931; Bounoure, 1940; Herlant-Meewis, 1946; Berrill and
762 Liu, 1948). These people made observations that did not fit into the simpler model of germ-
763 soma separation. Investigations (including some of Weismann's himself!) revealed gonad
764 regeneration or post-embryonic germ cell re-establishment where germline continuity
765 appeared broken (Berrill and Liu, 1948). As the modern synthesis of evolution gained more
766 traction, the idea of a continuous germline (protected from somatic contribution) helped
767 geneticists explain inheritance. Leo Buss notes that "the modern synthesis was virtually an
768 event unattended by embryologists", plant biologists, mycologists, people who studied colonial
769 invertebrates, which resulted in exclusion of these "oddities" from the modern synthesis of
770 evolution (Buss, 1988). Therefore, we left an interesting line of inquiry -a more complex model
771 of animal biology with germ cell regeneration and discontinuity- for another one: a simpler
772 dichotomous germ-soma separation that conveniently explained inheritance and genetics. I
773 argue it is now the right time we go back to these ignored complexities where, in some of these
774 organisms, germline is not strictly segregated and perhaps not even as protected as we have
775 come to accept. It will be interesting to see if this complexity has genomic integrity and
776 evolutionary repercussions, or whether animals have evolved to overcome potential
777 deleterious effects of regenerating their germline, and what these mechanisms are. It is time,
778 because several techniques and technologies available today enable us: Determining source
779 cells in regeneration is not only possible in an increasing number of genetically-tractable
780 organisms using genetic lineage tracing, but also possible with bioinformatics lineage-building
781 approaches via single cell RNAseq time series in those organisms where genetic lineage tracing
782 may not be feasible. Identifying precise sources of germ cell regeneration will allow us to
783 uncover cellular programming that underlies this process. As the regeneration of this cell type
784 has the potential to affect the next generation, investigations using sequencing and genomics
785 are possible to test whether the regenerated germ cells have higher mutation accumulation,
786 and whether this is a driving factor in evolution via introducing variation. From cellular
787 reprogramming to population genetics many exciting discoveries are within reach.

788

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BOX 1

Definitions

Germ cells (germline): The terms germ cells or germline are used for cells that include fully mature gametes, as well as any cell type leading up to gametes such as the embryonic precursor of the germline, primordial germ cells, germline stem cells etc...

Somatic cells (soma): Any cell type that does not contribute to the germ cell lineage under normal developmental conditions such as muscle, neurons, epidermis etc...

Gonads: The reproductive organs (ovaries and testes). Depending on the organism, these organs may have both somatic and germ components. In some examples reviewed here, it is difficult to know whether the gonads that regenerate include both cell types. I use this term when regeneration of the organ is tested, and I additionally indicate when the germ cells within gonads are also observed to regenerate.

Asexual reproduction (agametic): Reproduction without involvement of gametes, mating of sexes, and subsequent embryogenesis. In annelids, agametic asexual reproduction is observed as either paratomic fission or architomic fission. In paratomy, worms first build a new tail and a head, individuals still attached, these new tissues develop and clones eventually separate. In architomy, worms fragment themselves into several pieces, then rebuild missing parts. In the old annelid literature, sometimes this process is referred to as "regeneration". In this review, I use the term "regeneration" strictly for when an external insult removes a significant amount of tissue/body axis.

Stolonization: A mode of sexual reproduction found in specifically Syllid annelids, where stock worms produce a series of clones for sexual reproduction.

Regeneration: Renewal and restoration of lost tissues, organs, body parts and axes. I use regeneration when there is injury/removal of tissues/organs/body axes via an external factor and exclude rebuilding segments as a result of asexual reproduction from the definition of regeneration.

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